

FREQUENCY OF HYPOTHYROIDISM IN FEMALES WITH SUB-FERTILITY PRESENTING IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

Hafsa Batool^{*1}, Rashida Sultana², Asma Hameed³

^{*1,2,3}Department of Obstetrics & Gynecology, Chaudhary Akram Teaching and Research Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan

¹batoolhafsa636@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Hafsa Batool

Abstract

Objective: To determine the frequency of hypothyroidism in females with inability to conceive pregnancy who present in a tertiary care hospital.

Study Design: Cross-sectional study.

Study place and period: Department of Obstetrics & Gynecology, Chaudhry Muhammad Akram Teaching & Research Hospital, Lahore from 11th March 2025 to 10th June 2025.

Methodology: One hundred and twenty females fulfilled the inclusion criteria were included through OPD and blood sample was taken for assessment of thyroid function test. Reports were assessed and serum TSH level will be noted. If serum TSH >5 mIU/ml, then hypothyroidism was labeled. Data was initially recorded in proforma and analyzed in SPSS v.26. Frequency and percentage were calculated for hypothyroidism. Chi-square test was applied to compare hypothyroidism in stratified groups, with P-value ≤ 0.05 as significant.

Results: The median age of females was 30.00 (IQR: 13.00) years. The median duration of subfertility was 3.00 (IQR: 3.00) years and 66 (66%) had secondary subfertility. The median serum TSH level was 3.65 (IQR: 2.35) IU. Out of 120 females, 28 (23.3%) had hypothyroidism. Out of 28 females with hypothyroidism, 19 (67.9%) had subclinical hypothyroidism and 9 (32.1%) had overt hypothyroidism. There is no impact of age, BMI, family history, residence or occupation observed on occurrence of hypothyroidism (p>0.05).

Conclusion: The frequency of hypothyroidism in females of reproductive age group is high and not negligible.

INTRODUCTION

Elevated thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) and decreased tetraiodothyronine (T4) levels are the hallmarks of hypothyroidism.^{1, 2} Hashimoto's illness is the primary cause of hypothyroidism. Thyroid peroxidase, the enzyme in charge of iodine oxidation as the first stage of thyroid hormone synthesis, is the focus of this autoimmune disease. Autoantibodies against thyroglobuline, a macro-protein with 115 tyrosine residues and 5000 amino acids, are also generated in this illness.^{3, 4} The endometrium, ovulatory function, and fertility (from implantation to birth)

are all negatively impacted by thyroid gland malfunction.^{5, 6}

By directly promoting oocyte maturation and controlling prolactin and sex hormone binding globulin concentrations, thyroid hormones have an impact on female fertility. Of women of childbearing age, 1-2% have hyperthyroidism, 0.3% have overt hypothyroidism, and up to 15% have subclinical hypothyroidism. Anti-thyroid peroxidase and/or anti-thyroglobulin antibody concentrations are increased in about 10% of euthyroid women. In addition to affecting fertility,

hypothyroidism can create problems with ovulation and menstruation.^{7, 8} According to an Indian study, 27% of infertile women had hypothyroidism. Of these, 2.33% had overt hypothyroidism and 25% had subclinical hypothyroidism. About 52% of subclinical and 51.15% of overt hypothyroid women had menstrual disruption, with oligomenorrhea being the most common kind.⁹ According to a study done in Iraq, infertile women had a greater prevalence of thyroid hormone-related clinical manifestations (26.9%).¹⁰

The purpose of this study was to ascertain the prevalence of hypothyroidism in infertile females. The likelihood that hypothyroidism may result in infertility varies depending on the demographic, according to literature. However, the danger is twice in a neighboring country where health care facilities and lifestyle are nearly identical to those in Pakistan. However, there isn't much data accessible. Therefore, this study was conducted to obtain current data for the local population and use the findings in our context. By putting in place screening programs to lower the likelihood of hypothyroidism in females in our community who present with complaints of subfertility, this would help us obtain local evidence and enhance our practice.

METHODOLOGY

The study was started after obtaining ethical approval from ethical review committee of the hospital. This Cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Obstetrics & Gynecology, Chaudhry Muhammad Akram Teaching & Research Hospital, Lahore from from 11th March 2025 to 10th June 2025. Sample size of 120 cases is calculated with 95% confidence level, 8% margin of error and percentage of hypothyroidism i.e. 27% in females with subfertility.⁹ Non-probability, consecutive sampling techniques applied to enroll the females with following criteria:

Inclusion Criteria: Females of age 18-45 years, any parity, diagnosed with subfertility (primary and secondary subfertility) were enrolled in the study. Subfertility was defined as inability to conceive pregnancy after one year of unprotected sexual intercourse.

Exclusion Criteria: Females already taken treatment for hypothyroidism, or previous in-vitro fertilization, male subfertility with normal female factors or lack of consent were not included in the study.

Females were included through OPD and their informed consent was obtained before enrolment. Demographic data (age, parity, residence), duration of subfertility, family history of subfertility, family history of thyroid disorder were recorded. Then 1 ml venous blood sample was taken and was sent to the laboratory of the hospital for assessment of thyroid function test. Reports were assessed and serum TSH level was noted. If serum TSH >5 mIU/ml, then hypothyroidism was labeled. Subclinical hypothyroidism was labeled if serum TSH ranges from 4.6-20mIU/ml & normal free₄ it will be categorized as subclinical hypothyroidism. Overt hypothyroidism was labeled if serum TSH greater than 20mIU/ml it will be categorized as overt hypothyroidism. Females with hypothyroidism were managed as per standard protocol in collaboration with endocrinologist. All the data was recorded in proforma and confidentiality of data was ensured. SPSS version 26.0 was used to enter and analyze the collected data. Shapiro-Wilk test was applied to determine the normality of data. Mean and standard deviation were calculated for quantitative variable like age, duration of subfertility and TSH level. Frequency and percentage were calculated for parity, residence, family history of infertility or subfertility, family history of thyroid disorder and hypothyroidism. Data was stratified for age, duration of subfertility, parity, family history of infertility or subfertility, family history of thyroid disorder. Post-stratification, chi-square test / Fischer exact test was applied to compare hypothyroidism in stratified groups. P-value ≤ 0.05 was taken as significant.

RESULTS

In this study, we included total 120 females with complaint of subfertility. The median age of females was 30.00 (IQR: 13.00) years. The mean BMI of females was 28.00 (IQR: 7.00) kg/m², showing more females of overweight or obese category. Among all, 39 (32.5%) were nulliparous (primary subfertility) and 41 (34.2%) had 1 child

and 40 (33.3%) had 2 children. Out of 120 females, 73 (60.8%) were housewives and mostly (80.8%) were living in urban areas. The median duration of subfertility was 3.00 (IQR; 3.00) years and 81 (67.5%) had secondary subfertility. Family history of subfertility was found in 15 (12.5%) females and family history of thyroid disease was found in 20 (16.7%). The median serum TSH level was 3.65 (IQR: 2.35) IU. Table-I

Out of 120 females, 28 (23.3%) had hypothyroidism. Figure-1

Out of 28 females with hypothyroidism, 19 (67.9%) had subclinical hypothyroidism and 9 (32.1%) had overt hypothyroidism. Figure-2

Hypothyroidism was significantly higher in females with age more than 25 years [24 (28.9%)] than young ones (less than 25 years old), 4 (10.8%). Although hypothyroidism was more common in obese females 23 (24.5%) as compared to non-obese females 5 (19.2%), but the difference was insignificant ($p>0.05$). There is also no impact of occupation and residence observed on occurrence of hypothyroidism ($p>0.05$). Similarly, duration of subfertility, type of subfertility, family history of subfertility and family history of thyroid disease also had no significant relationship with occurrence of hypothyroidism ($p>0.05$). Table-II

Table-I: Basic demographics of females (n = 120)

Parameters	Statistic
Age, years	30.00 (IQR: 13.00)
BMI, kg/m ²	28.00 (IQR: 7.00)
Parity	
Nulliparous	39 (32.5%)
Para 1	41 (34.2%)
Para 2	40 (33.3%)
Occupation	
Housewife	73 (60.8%)
Working woman	47 (39.2%)
Residence	
Rural	23 (19.2%)
Urban	97 (80.8%)
Duration of subfertility, years	3.00 (IQR; 3.00)
Type of subfertility	
Primary	39 (32.5%)
Secondary	81 (67.5%)
Family history of subfertility	15 (12.5%)
Family history of thyroid disease	20 (16.7%)
Serum TSH	3.65 (IQR: 2.35)

Figure-1: Hypothyroidism (n = 120)

Figure-2: Type of hypothyroidism (n = 23)

Table-II: Association of hypothyroidism with effect modifiers (n = 120)

		Hypothyroidism		p-value
		Yes n = 28	No n = 92	
Age, years	18-25	4 (10.8%)	33 (89.2%)	0.030
	>25	24 (28.9%)	59 (71.1%)	
BMI	Obese	23 (24.5%)	71 (75.5%)	0.576
	Non-obese	5 (19.2%)	21 (80.8%)	
Occupation	Housewife	15 (20.5%)	58 (79.5%)	0.369
	Working woman	13 (27.7%)	34 (72.3%)	
Residence	Rural	5 (21.7%)	18 (78.3%)	0.841
	Urban	23 (23.7%)	74 (76.3%)	
Duration of subfertility	≤5 years	18 (20.5%)	70 (79.5%)	0.216
	>5 years	10 (31.3%)	22 (68.8%)	
Type of subfertility	Primary	6 (15.4%)	33 (84.6%)	0.153
	Secondary	22 (27.2%)	59 (72.8%)	
Family history of subfertility	Yes	4 (26.7%)	11 (73.3%)	0.744
	No	24 (22.9%)	81 (77.1%)	
Family history of thyroid disease	Yes	4 (20.0%)	16 (80%)	0.699
	No	24 (24.0%)	76 (76.0%)	

DISCUSSION

In our study, we observed hypothyroidism in 23.3% females of reproductive age group presented with complaint of subfertility. Out of 28 females with hypothyroidism, 19 (67.9%) had subclinical hypothyroidism and 9 (32.1%) had overt hypothyroidism. We also observed that there is no association of any BMI, family history, residence or occupation on the occurrence of hypothyroidism ($p > 0.05$). But age above 25 years was significantly associated with hypothyroidism. According to an Indian study, 27% of infertile women had hypothyroidism. Of these, 2.33% had overt hypothyroidism and 25% had subclinical hypothyroidism. 52% of subclinical and 51.15% of overt hypothyroid women had menstrual disruption, with oligomenorrhea being the most common kind.⁹ According to a study done in Iraq, infertile women had a greater prevalence of thyroid hormone-related clinical manifestations (26.9%).¹⁰

According to Ajaz et al., 29.6% of women had hypothyroidism. BMI and hypothyroidism were shown to be significantly correlated ($p = 0.026$), with a higher frequency in women whose BMI was greater than 25 kg/m². Higher prevalence of

hypothyroidism were also substantially correlated with primary infertility ($p = 0.025$).¹¹ However, in our study, we did not observed any relationship of BMI and type of infertility with hypothyroidism in young females. According to a research by Verma et al. comprising 394 women who initially visited an infertility clinic, TSH testing revealed that 23.9% of the patients had hypothyroidism.¹² In a similar vein, Kumari et al. found that 11.9% of infertile women had hyperthyroidism and 22.4% had hypothyroidism.¹³

Additionally, Ali et al. found that 28.5% of females had hypothyroidism, with 7.7% having overt hypothyroidism and 20.8% having subclinical hypothyroidism. Despite the lack of substantial correlations with common reproductive or demographic characteristics, they came to the conclusion that thyroid dysfunction, especially subclinical hypothyroidism, is very common in women with secondary infertility. These results confirm that routine thyroid monitoring is a crucial part of evaluating infertility.¹⁴ On the other hand, Naib et al. found that just 0.084% of females had hypothyroidism. Since over half of the identified patients had subclinical hypothyroidism, they came to the

conclusion that TSH should be performed early in the subfertility workup. Ignoring this issue results in needless medication, invasive tests, and psychological strain on the pair.¹⁵

In contrast to wealthy nations, where primary subfertility is more common, secondary subfertility was shown to be the most prevalent form, which is consistent with other studies from the developing world.^{16, 17} Additionally, secondary infertility was shown to be more prevalent (67.5%) than primary infertility in our study. Because subclinical hypothyroidism is more common in infertile women, it is recommended that subclinical hypothyroidism be routinely screened for in these women.^{18, 19} According to Western research, between 3 and 8% of people have subclinical hypothyroidism.²⁰ In contrast, research from India has revealed that the prevalence of SCH ranges from 9 to 32%.^{21, 22}

In this study, we faced few limitations. First of all sample size of the study was small (n = 120), whereas the number of cases with complaint of infertility is increasing day by day. Further studies should be done with larger sample size. Moreover, we did not check the effect of dietary factors and lifestyle of females on occurrence of hypothyroidism. However, these factors could affect the prevalence of hypothyroidism, especially young females (<30 years old).

CONCLUSION

The frequency of hypothyroidism in females of reproductive age group is high and not negligible. Thus it is found to be one of the major cause of subfertility in females of reproductive age group. No we will recommend to implement the screening programs to decrease the chances of hypothyroidism in females of our community presenting with complaint of subfertility.

Conflict of Interest: None

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